

To the Polemic of the Methodological Basis for Estimating the Investment Potential of Regions

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Abstract: In a market economy, the importance of the investment process at the macro, micro, regional and municipal levels is increasing. In the existing scientific works there is no common opinion on the definition of the terms "investment potential", "investment attractiveness" and "investment climate". Hence follows a different approach to their assessment. At the moment, there is no scientific basis for the methodological provisions for assessing the investment potential of the regions. Also, each method uses a different set of considered indicators that characterize the investment potential of the region.

Keywords: investments, investment potential, investment attractiveness, investment climate, methodology.

INTRODUCTION

When assessing investment potential, it is necessary to take into account many factors, such as the infrastructural development of the territory, innovative potential, intellectual potential of the population and the resource component. Therefore, a comprehensive approach is required to study the investment conditions of the region in order to bring them into an ordered system of interrelations, as well as to determine their impact on the level of competitiveness and demand for the regional economy in the capital market. All this actualizes the study of the problems of socio-economic assessment of the investment potential of the region, which is the basis for making management decisions at the regional level.

The purpose of this scientific article is to determine the advantages and problematic elements of the methods of assessing the investment potential of a region based on the analysis of the controversies of economists on the issue of methods of assessing the investment potential of a region, which is of great methodological importance.

To achieve this goal, a number of tasks were set before the study in this scientific article:

- study of theoretical approaches to the essence of the investment potential of a region;
- characteristics of the existing controversies of authors on the issue of methods of assessing the investment potential of a region;
- determination of the advantages and disadvantages of methods of assessing the investment potential of a region.

Currently, in the context of globalization and modernization of the economy, the importance of the investment process at the regional and municipal levels is increasing. Investments contribute to the development of production and infrastructure, as well as one of the fundamental factors in improving the standard of living of the population - the creation of new jobs. Given this circumstance, this scientific article will consider the methods of assessing the investment potential of a region, their advantages and disadvantages.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Today, there are many definitions of the term "investment potential" in economic literature, since there is no single approach to explaining investment potential. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the various positions on the interpretation of the concept under study by scientists in economic publications. But first, let us define the concepts of its constituent elements, namely "investments" and "potential".

The definition of the concept "potential" in the explanatory dictionary of economic terms is interpreted as follows:

- "power", which is manifested in the concept of "degree of power";
- "opportunity", intersecting with two categories such as "hidden opportunities" and "resources". This meaning of the concept "potential" is the main one and characterizes most interpretations of this concept.

There are many approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "investments".

Let us highlight the most general features that are inherent in this term: potential ability to generate income; purposefulness of investments; use of various resources for investing; risk; urgency of investments [1].

Further, it will be natural to study the very concept of "investment potential".

The term "investment potential" first appeared in the 1980s in the works of T.S. Khachaturov and V.P. Krasovsky, in which this concept was equated with a complex of asset-creating industries. However, these works do not reveal the essence of the economic content of this term [2].

Authors often consider the concept as the ability of a region to satisfy the need for the acquisition of investment resources without using borrowed capital and attracting borrowed funds. This definition can be interpreted as a set of production factors and capital inflow industries available in the region. This is a quantitative assessment that takes into account the macroeconomic indicators of the region such as saturation with such production factors (natural resources, labor force, fixed assets, infrastructure, etc.), as well as consumer demand of the population, etc. [3].

Another approach to determining investment potential is considered on the basis of the theory of comparative and absolute advantages, which lies in the combined ability of industry resources to increase the capital intensity of labor and the ability of the region, supervising these resources, to ensure economic growth in the form of income in a timely manner.

D.S. Beznos considers the investment potential of a region as one of the qualitative characteristics of the overall regional economic potential, which is due to the relationship of existing and potentially possible sources of investment financing for the region with a set of developed investment projects presented in the form of economically and socially sound directions for the use of investment resources "[3]. At the same time, D.S. Beznos notes that, in his opinion, the most concise and capacious definition is the interpretation of O.V. Khmyz - the ability to obtain the maximum possible volume of the investment component of the

gross regional product (GRP), realized through the use of investment factors of economic growth. This content includes the result component, which consists in the growth of GRP and the process component, in which this growth is observed due to the general efforts of the driving levers of the economy, resources and conditions for the implementation of investment projects in relation to a specific region [3].

The most widely used is the resource approach to determining investment potential. According to it, investment potential is considered in close connection with investment resources - the sources of its origin. Investment resources are a set of material, financial, intellectual resources that participate in the processes of accumulation, investment of capital with the aim of obtaining economic benefits, social or environmental effects in the future" [8, p. 45]. It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of investment potential and investment attractiveness.

O. G. Ulturgasheva, A. V. L. Avrenko, D. A. Profatilov give the following formulation: ". The investment potential of a region is the combined ability of its own and attracted economic resources to ensure, in the presence of a favorable investment climate, investment activity for the purposes and on a scale determined by the socio-economic policy of the region" [9, p. 227].

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

There is one interesting interpretation of investment potential in economics, which will be used to characterize possible future investments that may indirectly depend on previously accumulated capital, although this dependence will not be expressed linearly. This interpretation is supported by A.Kh. Shidov, who describes investment potential as a set of investments that can be attracted to the fixed capital of a region through all sources of financing (internal and external), based on the presence of differences in natural, economic and social resources in the region, the peculiarities of the geographical location and other factors.

From the point of view of economic theory, the investment potential of a region can be characterized by demand and supply. Based on the theory, the main component of investment activity is achieving equilibrium between demand and supply. Demand, in turn, is divided into potential and specific. Potential demand is understood as the volume of investment capital (investment resources), which is determined in accordance with the purchasing power of the population and the totality of investment needs. This demand arises in the absence of the intention of the business entity to direct the existing income (profit) to the goals of accumulation. The authors call it formal and give a definition as a source for future investment. In turn, specific demand is understood as the real supply of

Fig. 1 – Structure of the investment potential of the region

Moreover, economic theory implies the presence of a direct connection between investment potential and its specific implementation. In this regard, it should be noted that the implementation of investment potential, along with measures to ensure its formation and increase in level, also implies a set of measures to create conditions for its inclusion in the real investment process and the process of effective implementation through motivation of investment potential [3].

In our opinion, the investment potential of a region is considered as the combined ability of its own and attracted funds, given a favorable investment climate, to ensure investment activities for the purposes and on the scale determined by the investment policy of the region. In our understanding, the nature of the investment potential of a region (IPR) is dual: the volume of investment resources of a region, on the one hand, and the objects of investment of these resources, presented in the form of a kind of "regional investment portfolio of projects", on the other. In other words, it is appropriate to call these elements the "resource component of the IPR" and the "project (object) component of the IPR".

The resource component of the IPR should consist of two components:

- the potential for mobilizing investment resources by existing economic entities - the total volume of existing and possible funds for investing in the regional economy;
- the potential for mobilizing investment resources by latent companies - potential investment investments of those entrepreneurs who plan to create a new business.

In turn, the project component of the IPR consists of two types of investment projects that have been developed, as well as those in the active development stage, depending on the scale of implementation:

- the availability of economically and socially sound investment projects of local significance;
- the availability of economically and socially sound investment projects of regional significance.

In turn, the totality of the investment potential of all regions forms the overall investment potential of the country, which is necessary, first of all, for foreign investors [3].

Also, summarizing various points of view, it can be noted that investment potential consists

of the following potentials: resource-raw materials; labor; production; innovation; institutional; infrastructure; financial; consumer. The resource approach is the basis for most of the studies on the problem of assessing investment potential, for which several private potentials are distinguished in its composition (raw materials, production, infrastructure, labor, innovation, financial, etc.), and the assessment is based on the quantitative or index measurement of indicators of private potentials. The same assessment principle underlies the ranking of economic systems (territories, industries) by rating and analytical agencies. The key advantage of this approach is the possibility of quantitative assessments of the investment potential of an economic system at any level (country, region, industry, enterprise).

A significant disadvantage of the resource approach to assessing investment potential is its methodological similarity with the economic categories of "national wealth", "material and technical base", "resources". In other words, the concepts of "investment resources" and "investment potential" are identical. However, resources exist independently of the subjects of economic activity, while potential is inseparable from them, i.e. the term "potential", including resources, also characterizes the possibility and/or ability of the economic system to use them effectively. It should be noted that the concept of "potential" has a dual nature and is interpreted as the unity of qualitative and quantitative certainty. Quantitative certainty of investment potential can be designated by the term "investment resources".

At present, there are several methods for assessing the investment potential of a region. It is customary to distinguish three groups of methods for diagnosing conditions and factors influencing regional development: methods of factor analysis, expert assessments, and economic and mathematical methods.

Mathematical methods:

1. The sum of places method - ranking regions by indicators that characterize investment potential. The best values are awarded first place. The ranking of regions is determined by the sum of places for all indicators.
2. The method of point assessments differs from the previous one in that the regions with the best values of the indicators are assigned the highest points.

A major drawback of these methods is the difference between the nearest regions in the ranked row assessed at the same point, despite the fact that the difference in some places may be more significant.

3. The multivariate average method takes into account the shortcomings of the previous methods - for each indicator, the average value for the country is calculated, then the indicators of the regions are compared with it. Thus, each region is assigned its own coefficient.

4. The "Pattern" method differs from the previous one in that the best values are taken as the basis for the standardized values of the indicators, and not the average indicators for the country. The main advantage of the listed methods is their ease of use, however, they have a serious drawback - the indicators are included in the model without justification, and it is also impossible to determine the contribution of each indicator to the final assessment.

Also, statistical methods are used to study hidden phenomena and relationships in the regional economy, which are represented by sets of observed values, which are united by the general term - "factor analysis". This analysis includes the following models: factor and regression.

In factor analysis, the emphasis is on studying the internal causes that shape the specificity of the phenomenon under consideration. In this analysis, all features are considered as equivalent. Factor analysis is used to study models that are difficult to reflect quantitatively using a one-dimensional model.

Regression analysis focuses on determining the weight of each feature that influences the result, and its impact (quantitatively), all other things being equal [5, p. 1.37]. The most popular and practically applied are the methods of expert assessments. Among them, the following can be distinguished:

- the method of the rating agency "E.expert RA";
- the method of assessing the investment climate of Russian regions of the Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

Methodology of the rating agency "Expert RA". In this methodology, two characteristics are adopted as the main components of the investment attractiveness of regions: investment risk and investment potential. The value of investment potential is determined by the values of nine particular potentials of the region: natural resource, labor, institutional, infrastructure, financial, production, innovation, tourism and consumer. Each of them is described by a set of various indicators. The R.ang of each region is determined by a quantitative assessment of its potential, as a share in the total potential of all regions of the country. Investment risk is the probability of investment losses and income from them. It is an integral indicator that combines seven private types of risks - economic, financial, social, environmental, managerial, criminal and legislative. The rank of a region by risk type is determined by the value of the investment risk index - the relative deviation from the average risk level for the country, which is taken as a unit [6, p. 4.3]. The result of the methodology is a formed rating, according to which all regions considered in the "potential - risk" plane are distributed into groups (Fig. 1).

The most favorable regions are those belonging to cell 1A, the least favorable — to cell 3D.

The main advantage of this methodology is the coverage of a large number of factors in the investment process. Factors are taken into account with the help of expert assessments and comparative characteristics. Many of them are not subject to mathematical measurement. This indicates the complexity and, consequently, the significant reliability of the assessments. The disadvantage of the methodology is the subjectivity of expert opinions when conducting the assessment, as well as the lack of transparency in the assessment of investment potential and risks (the calculation system and the indicators used are not published in open sources).

Investment potential	Investment risk			
	1A	1B	1C	3D
	2A	2B	2C	
	3A	3B1	3C1	
3B2		3C2		
Attractiveness rating	Description			
1A	Maximum potential - minimum risk			
1B	High potential - moderate risk			
1C	High potential - high risk			
2A	Average potential - minimum risk			
2B	Average potential - moderate risk			
2C	Average potential - high risk			
3A	Low potential - minimum risk			
3B1	Reduced potential - moderate risk			
3B2	Insignificant potential - moderate risk			
3C1	Reduced potential - high risk			
3C2	Insignificant potential - high risk			
3D	Low potential - extreme risk			

Fig. 1. Distribution of regions by investment potential groups[12, p. 75]

Methodology of the Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

To assess the investment climate of a region, the Institute of Economics of the Russian Academy of Sciences uses 75 partial factors of the regional investment climate (65 expertly assessed and 10 statistical), which are reduced to seven blocks:

- "A" - factors of economic potential;
- "B" - business conditions;
- "C" - formation of the market environment;
- "G" - political factors;
- "D" - social and socio-cultural factors;
- "E" - organizational and legal factors;
- "G" - financial factors.

The level of factors determined by expert witnesses is assessed on a six-point scale: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. To conduct the survey, a contingent of expert witnesses is formed, which is divided into five groups according to socio-professional characteristics:

- 1) scientists, university professors and designers;
 - 2) employees of the lending sector;
 - 3) managers of small and medium-sized enterprises;
 - 4) employees of state authorities and local governments;
 - 5) directors of large industrial enterprises. The statistical indicators are assessed as follows. Each region is compared with other regions by a certain indicator, and based on the comparison the region is awarded a point. The region with the best indicator automatically receives 5 points; the region with the lowest value among all receives 0; the average values of the indicators are assessed at 2.5 points. The remaining points are awarded in the same way, based on proportions.
1. The obtained averages from the assessments for each expertly determined factor and each of the statistical indicators are multiplied by the "weight" (the degree of influence of this factor on the investment climate). "Weights" are supposed to be established by experts based on a survey of well-known economists dealing with investment issues.
 2. A set of weighted average assessments for all factors is summed up and represents a summary indicator of the investment climate of the region (Q). Then an ordinal scale of the location of regions in descending order of the Q indicator is compiled, which is the rating of regions by the level of investment climate.
 3. As an advantage, it can be noted that thanks to this method, it is possible to obtain fairly accurate results when analyzing a small number of regions.
 4. The main disadvantage of this method is the excessive focus on expert opinions, the difficulty of attracting a large number of experts and the low share of statistical indicators.
 5. Based on the methods considered, for clarity, a table can be compiled by groups of methods with a description of their positive and negative sides (Table 1).

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of methods for assessing the investment potential of regions*

Group of methods	Strengths	Weaknesses
Economic and mathematical methods	Ease of use, universality, clarity. The methods are convenient for research at the macroeconomic level	The difference between the closest regions in the ranking series is estimated at one point, despite the fact that the difference may be much more significant. The indicators are included in the models without justification, and there is no way to determine the contribution of each indicator to the final assessment
Factor analysis methods	Bringing individual indicators to a comparable form	Many qualitative indicators and all weighting factors in the model are determined taking into account expert assessments.
Methods of expert assessments	Coverage of a large number of factors of the investment process, factors are taken into account using expert assessments and comparative characteristics	Difficulty in attracting a large number of experts and a low share of statistical indicators, subjectivity of expert opinions

*Author's development.

CONCLUSIONS

1. When assessing the investment potential, it is necessary to take into account many factors, such as the infrastructural development of the territory, innovative potential, intellectual potential of the population and the resource component. Therefore, a comprehensive approach is required to study the investment conditions of the region in order to bring them into an orderly system of interrelations, as well as to determine their impact on the level of competitiveness and demand for the regional economy in the capital market.
2. At the moment, there is no scientific substantiation of the methodological provisions for assessing and analyzing the investment potential of regions.
3. Each method uses a different set of indicators that characterize investment attractiveness. Economic and mathematical methods do not use qualitative indicators, and expert assessment methods rely on the opinions of "experts", which can often be subjective.
4. All this suggests that today it is difficult to objectively assess the real investment potential of a region using only one assessment method.

References:

1. Konoplitsky V.A., Filina. A.I. This is business, explanatory dictionary of economic terms - 4th ed. / V.A. Konoplitsky, A.I. Filina // Reference publication. - Kyiv: KNT, 2017. - 624 p.
2. Serikov S.G. Investment potential of the region / S.G. Serikov // Economy and entrepreneurship. - Moscow, 2015. - No. 3-2 (5b-2). - P. 220- 222.
3. Beznos D.S. Resource and project approaches to determining the essence of the investment potential of the region / D.S. Beznos // Scientific statements of the Belgorod

- State University. Series: Economy. Informatics. - Belgorod, 2014. - No. 8-1 (179). - P. 42-46.
4. Ayroyan R.G. Investment potential and investment risks as the main components of the investment climate / R.G. Ayroyan, T.G. Popadyuk // Innovative science. - Moscow, 201b.- No. 2-1. - P. 15-17.
 5. Ulturgasheva O. G. Economic essence and structure of the investment potential of the region / O. G. Ulturgasheva, A. V. Lavrenko // Problems of modern economy. - Moscow, 2014. - No. 1. - P. 60-63.
 6. Neshitoy A. S. Investments: Textbook. - 8th ed., revised. and corrected. - M.: Publishing and trading corporation "Dashkov and Co.", 2017. - 453 p.
 7. Doroshenko Yu.A. Economic potential of the territory. - 4th ed. St. Petersburg, Business and Service, 2014. - 431 p.
 8. Tkachenko I. N., Starikov E. N. Model of integrated assessment of the potential of the regional industry complex // Bulletin of the Irkutsk State University of Economics. 2008. No. 2, pp. 45-48
 9. Ulturgasheva, O. G., Lavrenko A. V., Profatilov D. A. Economic essence and structure of the investment potential of the region // Problems of modern economy - 2011 - No. 1 - pp. 227-229. [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ekonomicheskaya-suschnost-i-struktura-investitsionnogo-potentsiala-regiona>
 10. Blum, E. A. Review of methods for assessing the investment potential of a region // Young scientist. - 2013. - No. 7. - pp. 137-141. [Electronic resource]. URL: <http://moluch.ru/archive/54/7388/>
 11. Litvinova, V. V. Investment attractiveness and investment climate of a region: monograph. Moscow: Financial University, 2013. - 116 p.
 12. Zinovieva N.M. Investment potential of a region as a basis for ensuring investment activity (on the example of the Belgorod region) / N.M. Zinovieva, E.G. Karaichentseva // Territory of Science. - Voronezh, 201b. - №2. - P. 74-78.
 13. Dzhamalov H.N. Diagnostics of the financial health of small businesses // Journal of Economy and Business, vol. 1-1 (71), 2021. P. 99-104